

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

Follow up report on the activities of the task 1.4

Milestone 4: First farmers consultation summary elaborated

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement n° 101112951.

www.project-credible.eu

DISCLAIMER: The views expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views or position of the European Union. Neither the authors nor the CREDIBLE consortium are responsible for the use which might be made of the information contained in here.

Title

How is the European farmer community receiving carbon farming strategies so far?

Authors

Juan Sagarna (Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España)

Celeste Oliveira (Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España)

Kaj Gronholm (Baltic Sea Action Group)

Clara Diebolt (Réseau des Chambres d'agriculture de l'arc atlantique)

Daniel Ács (Bioeconomy Clusters)

Key messages

- The agricultural and livestock sector is traditional and generally struggles to move away from the inertia of activities that undergo small and gradual changes over time.
- The average farmer is currently somewhat frustrated with excessive regulation and too many changes in a short period. This impacts carbon farming, even though it is a voluntary initiative.
- Farmers are sceptical of emerging markets. They are used to seeing economic results tied to the yields of their main crops, and it feels unfamiliar to think they could receive market benefits for producing something as intangible as carbon.
- Carbon farming aligns synergistically with the growing awareness over recent decades of the need to improve soil care, a conviction shared by most farmers.
- The lack of concrete examples at a local level and within the same sectors as individual farmers undermines their confidence in these activities.
- Amongst farmers already doing benefit practices for soil health there are both frustration and incomprehension about the difficulties to consider their efforts regarding “Additionality” in carbon farming schemes.

- Farmers are eager to receive additional or complementary payments for practices adoption, whenever it does not require fundamental changes to how they manage their farms or compromise business even in the short term.
- Practices more suitable for wider adoption are crop rotations, mulching and organic fertilisation, if the economic balance in the farm allows it. Progressively reducing tillage is an actual trend in agriculture and sometimes ends in no tillage but this last step faces local and soil constraints. Livestock sector struggles to participate in carbon farming directly with grassland and pasture management or providing raw material for organic-based fertilizers.
- Farmers' organisations, which are assumed to have greater strategic capacity and long-term vision, do recognise the opportunities provided by public support for these strategies and participate actively to secure additional funds beyond those from the Common Agricultural Policy, which they consider insufficient to sustain a competitive agriculture.

Introduction

Carbon farming is a predominantly voluntary initiative. Farmers, as key players in the productive sector within the agri-food value chain, must be convinced that carbon farming provides them with tangible benefits and that the barriers to its adoption today can be overcome. The main objective of Task 1.4 of the CREDIBLE project is to gauge the current perception of farmers and their expectations regarding carbon farming, aiming to draw conclusions about its weaknesses, opportunities, threats, and strengths. To achieve this, an analysis of the available information has been conducted and updated, complemented by specific interviews with 38 experts, primarily in Spain but also significantly in Slovakia, Finland, France, and Italy. They were asked about their opinion as well as the farmers that they work with.

Current context

This document could be highly valuable in this crucial phase, early 2025. It is not only the European Commission and the expert group it has established that are making

decisions on the implementation of the CFCR; in this context, it is essential to create a framework that appeals to farmers if its impact is to be effectively ensured.

Furthermore, the Commission President and the Commissioners responsible for Agriculture and Climate policies must put forward proposals in its new vision for agriculture and food that align with the key points identified in the Strategic Dialogue on Agriculture, which the main stakeholders agreed upon at the end of 2024.

In the new political landscape, there is growing recognition that European policies affecting rural areas cannot be implemented without the decisive input and active participation of farmers and their organisations. Even the best ideas and policies may fail if the elements that make them acceptable to farmers and secure their commitment are not properly identified.

From the perspective of farmers as potential users of carbon farming, the regulatory framework remains uncertain. The regulation governing certificates and their development through delegated acts has so far focused on the more general aspects, particularly the concept of QUALITY. However, as of the publication date of this document, no technical guidelines for the practical implementation of carbon farming by farmers are available, although these are expected in the near future. This lack of guidance presents an additional challenge for farmers and their organisations to assess the suitability of these practices for their operations.

Similarly, markets for these certificates are nascent or often non-existent. Farmers are aware of some examples of how voluntary markets operate in the United States, as well as early attempts in Europe to establish agreements on carbon sequestration certificates. However, these examples are insufficient for them to form a well-founded opinion on the economic impact of carbon farming on their farms.

Recommendations

- The interviews conducted reveal that the most significant barrier is the **lack of specific training** in agricultural and livestock practices that may not be familiar

or common in conventional farms. This highlights the need to establish a **network of practice demonstrators** within real farms.

- Another major barrier identified by the experts is the **unpredictability of payments**, as the markets where certificates could be traded are not yet clearly defined. The limited certainties available so far suggest a scenario of **insufficient payments** to cover the costs of transitioning to new practices, at least in the short term. In this regard, it is proposed to seek **synergies with other complementary payment schemes**, both public—such as eco schemes within the **Common Agricultural Policy**—and private, in emerging markets for **regenerative agriculture** or established ones for **organic farming**.
- It would be valuable to leverage the growing awareness within the agricultural sector of soil health to build resilience and ensure its fertility for the future. Synergies should be sought with other relevant trends that also **focus on SSM sustainable soil management**, such as regenerative agriculture, carbon farming, precision agriculture, conservation agriculture, and more.

Background information

The primary source of information was the 38 individual interviews conducted with experts. These experts had diverse profiles, but most were professionals with strong university training and approximately a decade of experience in the agri-food sector, including organising, training, and advising farmers. Directly surveying farmers' opinions would have required considerable statistical effort, with a sample that accounted for regional, sectoral, structural, and other variables. As a result, the project opted to gather this input indirectly through experts who could provide a well-informed perspective on the farmers and livestock producers they work with.

Most experts possess a deeper understanding of carbon farming compared to farmers, particularly regarding its regulatory and technical aspects, which made the interviews straightforward. Many of these experts have participated in carbon-related

projects, including certificate issuance in cases like France. Nonetheless, the primary goal of the interviews was to obtain the farmers' views.

According to the experts, farmers have a limited understanding of carbon farming, although some familiarity exists due to connections with EU Common Agricultural Policy eco-schemes, as in Spain, or earlier initiatives, as in France. Beyond the regulatory framework and strategic implications, farmers want greater certainty about specific techniques and how these can maintain high productivity while integrating a new revenue stream through carbon certificates.

As noted elsewhere in this report, farmers' opinions on carbon farming are both receptive and skeptical. This skepticism grows over time as early expectations—often exaggerated in initial communications—remain unfulfilled. Significant barriers exist across economic, technical, sociocultural, and regulatory domains. Farmers also express some resistance to “Brussels' mandates,” even though these are voluntary programmes.

The most significant barriers perceived by farmers include insufficient training in carbon farming and its practical integration on their farms. This concern matches their perception that financial rewards will be inadequate. On a secondary level, they highlight uncertainties around the markets for trading certificates, ensuring reliable payments, and the high upfront costs of equipment or complex certification procedures. Other potential issues, such as sharing confidential farm data, farm size limitations, or concerns about large corporations dominating agriculture, are not seen as major worries by farmers.

When it comes to drivers of carbon farming, the most prominent is the opportunity for supplementary income beyond traditional agricultural production. Equally important is the alignment of these practices with market demands and customer sustainability requirements, which increasingly focus on sustainable soil management (SSM) and other environmentally friendly practices.

The farmers and experts also expressed their opinion about usual techniques linked with carbon farming. In all of them they identified benefits and barriers pointing that

final uptake would depend on balance between efforts and rewards. Some of them are more specific and known by farmers such as crop rotation, reduced tillage, cover crops, meanwhile others are more innovative for them (biochar, intercropping, green manure) or are more comprehensive approach different from conventional farms (organic farming, agroforestry, peatland, wetland&grassland restoration and conservation). Within the analysis, crop rotation is the most well identified and wider adaptable technique to different situations, and so the one that farmers are more prone to bet on in the future. Cover crops have great potential also in carbon farming but lack bioclimatic specific solutions on agricultural species and management practices. Also mulching is well considered both for its soil function and crop residues management. For the same reason, livestock farmers stress the role of biofertilizers from animal residues and grasslands improved management practices.

Peatland, wetland and grassland conservation and restoration is a vital technique for sustainability and carbon sequestration, often paired with grassland conservation and agroforestry. While it aligns well with sustainable agriculture policies, its implementation is hindered by high costs, local adaptation needs, and unclear guidelines. Experts recognise its potential but note limited practical application due to underdeveloped markets and technical challenges. Despite these barriers, it remains a key strategy in advancing carbon farming objectives.

Agroforestry is recognised as an effective strategy for promoting sustainability and carbon sequestration by integrating trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes. It offers multiple benefits, including improved biodiversity, soil health, and resilience to climate change. The difficulty is to imply a thoroughly change in the way that some farms are currently designed and managed.

Cover and catch crops are widely recognised for their role in improving soil health, preventing erosion, and enhancing biodiversity and carbon storage. These practices are particularly valued for their ability to maintain ground cover during fallow periods in arable crops, reducing nutrient runoff and boosting overall farm sustainability. In permanent crops, especially in vineyards and orchards, it can align with broader agroecological goals but it is often hindered by challenges such as competition for

water in drought-prone areas and additional management requirements. Despite their benefits, adoption remains uneven due to limited technical knowledge, variable effectiveness depending on local conditions, and insufficient financial incentives. Experts view these crops as a key component of carbon farming strategies, with potential synergies alongside other sustainable practices. Greater technical guidance and economic support could significantly boost their uptake among farmers.

Crop rotation is a foundational practice in sustainable agriculture, offering benefits such as improved soil fertility, reduced pest pressures, and enhanced carbon storage. By alternating crops, farmers can diversify production and mitigate risks associated with monoculture systems. Its adoption, however, is often constrained by market demands, limited technical knowledge, and economic pressures to maximise short-term yields. Experts emphasise its role in carbon farming, particularly for its synergy with soil conservation and long-term sustainability goals. Expanding educational and research resources and aligning incentives with rotational practices could drive broader implementation and maximise its environmental and agronomic potential.

No tillage and reduced tillage practices are vital for preserving soil structure, reducing erosion, and enhancing carbon sequestration. By minimising soil disturbance, these methods help retain moisture, improve biodiversity, and lower greenhouse gas emissions. Despite their benefits, adoption is often limited by the need for specialised equipment, increased weed management requirements, increased use of glyphosate and variable results across soil types.

Organic farming systems are valued for their focus on ecological balance, biodiversity enhancement, and sustainable resource use. By avoiding synthetic inputs, they promote healthier soils, improved water quality, and greater carbon sequestration potential. However, their adoption can be hindered by higher labour demands, certification costs, and market access challenges. Experts see organic farming as a complementary approach within carbon farming strategies, particularly for its alignment with consumer demand for sustainable products. Expanding support for

training, certification processes, and market development could further encourage the adoption of organic practices.

Soil amendment with biochar not well known but already recognised for its potential to sequester carbon over the long term. By stabilising organic matter, biochar contributes to soil health and reduces greenhouse gas emissions. However, its adoption is limited by high production costs, inconsistent availability, and a lack of awareness among farmers.

Grassland management plays a key role in maintaining ecosystem health, improving forage quality, and enhancing carbon sequestration. Practices such as rotational grazing and controlled stocking rates help prevent overgrazing, support soil health, and promote biodiversity. However, challenges such as limited knowledge, variable outcomes based on local conditions, and economic constraints can hinder adoption. Increased access to technical support and financial incentives could encourage wider adoption and optimise its impact on both productivity and sustainability.

Intercropping is a sustainable agricultural practice that involves growing two or more crops together to enhance biodiversity, improve soil health, and optimise resource use. Not too much tested in Europe at farm scale. It offers benefits such as reduced pest pressure, better nutrient cycling, and increased carbon sequestration. However, its adoption can be constrained by challenges like complex management, potential competition between crops, and the need for tailored strategies for different systems.

Mulching is a beneficial practice in sustainable agriculture, involving the application of organic or inorganic materials to the soil surface to conserve moisture, reduce erosion, and suppress weeds. It enhances soil health by moderating temperature and promoting carbon retention. However, adoption can be limited by the cost and availability of suitable materials, as well as additional labour requirements. Experts highlight mulching as an effective technique within carbon farming, particularly in perennial crops and water-scarce regions. Increased support for material sourcing, training, and integration into broader farming systems could boost its adoption and maximise its environmental benefits.

Green manure involves planting cover crops that are later incorporated into the soil to improve fertility, structure, and carbon content. This practice supports sustainable agriculture by enhancing nutrient cycling, increasing organic matter, and reducing the need for synthetic fertilisers. However, adoption can be hindered by the opportunity cost of not planting cash crops and the need for specific technical knowledge.

Organic fertilisers and amendments play a vital role in sustainable agriculture by improving soil health, enhancing nutrient availability, and boosting carbon sequestration. Derived from natural sources like compost, manure, and plant residues, they contribute to long-term soil fertility and reduce reliance on synthetic inputs. However, their adoption can be limited by availability, variability in nutrient content, and higher labour requirements. Experts see organic amendments as a key component of carbon farming strategies, offering environmental and agronomic benefits. Broader access, standardisation, and financial incentives could drive wider use and maximise their impact on productivity and sustainability.

References

1. *38 interviews to experts and farmer's advisors carried out within CREDIBLE project task 1.4*
2. *Carbon Farming Schemes in Europe – Roundtable- Background document. Produced by ecologic, COWI and IEEP in 2019 for European Commission DG Clima*
3. *2nd Carbon Farming Roundtable-Background document. Elaborated by ecologic, COWI and IEEP in 2020 for European Commission DG Clima*
4. *In June 2021, COPA COGECA issues its first reflection paper on the carbon farming initiative.*
5. *The 15 of December 2021 was released COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT, Sustainable carbon cycles - Carbon farming, Accompanying the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council Sustainable Carbon Cycle*

6. Study requested by European parliament ENVI committee Carbon farming Making agriculture fit for 2030. Made by Ecologic Institute, IEEP
 7. The February 25th COPA COGECA(European Farmers & European agri-cooperatives) presented the position paper on carbon farming
 8. PPT presentation on January 2023 by project LIFE CARBON FARMING Making Agriculture Fit for 2030
 9. CARBON REMOVALS EXPERT GROUP TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE.
 10. POSITION COPA COGECA IN TRILOGUES
 11. POSITION ELO (European Landowners Organisation)IN TRILOGUES
 12. CEJA (European Council of Young Farmers)POSITION
 13. FARMER PERSPECTIVES ON CARBON MARKETS INCENTIVIZING AGRICULTURAL SOIL CARBON SEQUESTRATION
- <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-023-00055-4>

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

